

Comparative Study of Time-Series Transformation Methods for Diagnosis of Bearing Faults in Three-Phase Squirrel Cage Induction Motor

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ABSTRACT

The study proposes a qualitative comparison between different methods of Recurrence Plot (RP) image conversion to detect minor faults (such as bearing faults, inter turn faults etc.) in a three-phase squirrel cage induction motor in the form of a Convolutional Neural Network called 'MoRPNet.' This model is capable of providing real-time and non-invasive analysis in order to reduce downtime by ensuring predictive maintenance. MoRPNet is trained based on Modified RP images, which are obtained by capturing stator line currents signature from the inductor motor and then converting it to Park's Vector Alternating Current (PVAC) signal. The usefulness of this model may be further enhanced in order to detect other faults affecting the robustness of industrial equipment.

KEYWORDS: *Minor faults, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), MoRPNet, Real-time analysis, Predictive maintenance, Modified Recurrence Plot (RP), Park's Vector Alternating Current (PVAC), Stator line current.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Three Phase Squirrel Cage Induction Motors are considered to be one of the largest sinks of reactive as well as active power. So, being the mainspring of industrial applications, it possesses some structural and economic benefits. Along with minimum maintenance requirements, these motors are known for their robustness. However, unpredictable faults may cause a reduction in downtime and an increment in maintenance costs. For protection purposes, a traditional fault curing system is normally installed, which comprises sensing circuits and other protective equipment like relays, circuit breakers, etc. This mechanism enables the detection of major faults in the system, ensuring the safety of the equipment and boosting plant performance.

As discussed before, a traditional fault protection system detects major faults, possessing intensity of fault above a certain level. However, this methodology fails to detect minor faults such as bearing faults (misalignment fault, dry lubricant fault), overloading, overheating, inter-turn fault, etc. Tradition fault protection works on the basis of Motor Current Signature Analysis (MCSA), Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) (Lee et al., 2022), or Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Lee et al., 2022, Song et al., 2023). During any abnormal change in the magnitude of current or voltage, the relay senses the value and sends a tripping command to the circuit breaker, which further trips the line, causing pure isolation of the faulty portion from the healthy circuit.

Induction motors are not immune to internal and external faults, and that is why minor faults need to be taken into prime consideration. These faults, even though they have low intensity, may cause rapid deterioration in performance, which in turn causes reduced downtime, high maintenance cost, and even replacement of the equipment. Therefore, the requirement of Condition Based Monitoring is highly demanding in today's industry. This is a non-intrusive as well as non-invasive approach that facilitates vibration analysis, thermography, MCSA (Yatsugi et al., 2023), and ultrasound testing in order to detect faults without shutdown and disassembly of the machinery. The overall lifespan and reliability are boosted

by preventing major breakdowns and optimizing maintenance schedules; Hence, overall operational efficiency gets boosted.

From numerous research analyses, it is stated that bearing fault is the most occurring minor fault (approximately 30%) (Neupane et al., 2021, Lee et al., 2021). In this study, a specific comparison of time series image conversion methods is stated, utilizing the extended Park vector modulus (PVAC). The PVAC method involves extracting the stator line currents of the squirrel cage induction motor and converting them into a Park vector modulus signal. This signal is further transformed into a 2D recurrence plot image using some modified formulae, capturing the temporal dynamics and intricate patterns associated with different bearing fault conditions. The conversion methods that are going to be compared are:

1. Spectrogram
2. Gramian Angular Field
3. Markov Field Transition

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND:

Bearings in induction motors reduce friction between moving parts and facilitate the rotation of the rotor. Thus, a reliable and smooth operation is ensured for the presence of bearing. These faults may be caused by various factors such as manufacturing defects, improper installation, contamination, and inadequate lubrication, resulting in vibrational losses and unwanted noise and may cause permanent failure of the motor. This study focuses on one of the bearing faults.

2.1 *Misalignment Between Inner and Outer Races of a Bearing*

Misalignment within a bearing structure directly hampers the performance of induction motors. This fault occurs due to incorrect alignment of geometric centrelines of the bearing races, resulting in either angular or parallel misalignment (Mohammed et al., 2021, Lee et al., 2023, Zhou et al., 2023). Angular misalignment occurs when races lean relatively towards each other, causing uneven stress distribution and localized wear, while parallel misalignment involves a lateral displacement of the races, leading to abnormal force application on the bearing elements. The undistributed force causes external pressure, which in turn produces unwanted losses and rotational malfunction (Kumar et al., 2019). These minor faults are rapidly circulating in nature, and in the absence of proper monitoring, the machine may get damaged, affecting performance parameters associated with it.

Figure 1: Misalignment Fault in Bearing

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In the experiment to determine differed bearing faults, an experimental setup is installed where a 2hp, 415V, 3-phase squirrel cage star-connected induction motor is used. This motor is mechanically coupled with a 1hp DC generator with four incandescent bulbs as load (so that load behavior remains linear throughout the experiment). A 3-phase-balanced supply is used by the use of three single-phase autotransformers, which help in maintaining the balanced supply condition. The stator line current through the motor is monitored using three-phase digital power meter (YOKOGAWA WT300E) equipped with the induction motor and PC.

During each experiment, the stator line current has been captured for 2.5 cycles under steady state condition at a sampling frequency of 20KHz. However, for a modified PVAC signal, only one cycle is considered. This study focuses on the misalignment of races of bearing, and thus, two sets of experiments are considered.

Figure 2: Experimental Setup

3.1 Healthy Situation:

A reference is required to diagnose the fault. The preliminary experiment is done by capturing some data during a healthy state. Five different loadings have been considered, gradually increasing from no load (L0) to full load (L4). For each condition, 10 instances are considered, and hence, a total of 50 data are taken into consideration. The conditions are scripted as H_NL_i to H_L4_i, where i ranges from 1 to 10.

3.2 Faulty Situation:

In the next step, a bearing with misalignment between the inner and outer races is used instead of a healthy bearing. With such a faulty configuration, a set of data has been captured. The motor is run for 525 minutes (8.75 hours) in total, considering different loading conditions.

The experiment has been divided into three zones. The bearing is faulty in nature, and we are meant to provide as much stress as possible to the bearing in order to fully utilize the obtainable data to perform a comparison study. The zones are based on the run time of the machine. The initial zone has a runtime of 184 minutes, where four sets of data are considered. Similarly, two other zones, i.e., intermediate and final zones, are considered for 179 minutes and 162 minutes, respectively. These two zones contain four and three sets of data, respectively.

The nomenclature of each set is done based on the no. of sets considered and the load number. Zone-1 and Zone-2 possess four sets, each where each set contains a total of 5 different loading conditions. For each loading condition, a total of 10 readings are considered. So, the readings are represented from IR1_NL_0 to IR11_L4_10.

Figure 3: Flow Chart

Figure 4(a): Healthy Situation (at 100% load); Figure 4(b): Faulty Situation (Zone-2, at 100% load)

4. METHODOLOGY

As the flow chart states, the three-phase current is extracted from the induction motor, which is further normalized for a single cycle, followed by generating a PVAC (Park's Vector AC Component) signal. The PVAC signal is used to create a modified RP (MoRP) image. In this study, three image conversion methods are considered. For each sample, 2.5 cycles have been considered. One out of the three phases have been considered as a reference in order to nullify the possibility of disparity between images of the same class. The single-cycle extraction is done using a MATLAB script. The below figures show the extracted line currents in healthy as well as faulty situations.

In this experiment, we are utilizing the Extended Park's Vector method to convert the stator line currents (a) of the induction motor into a 1-D signal Park's (b) Vector AC (PVAC) signal, which is then used for fault detection. PVAC signals can capture the magnitude of current quickly and, hence, can detect minor faults like misalignment or dry lubricant situations, which are not easily detectable changes in the individual stator current components.

$$PVM = \sqrt{I_d^2 + I_q^2}$$

The process of PVAC Signal generation requires Park's transformation (also known as DQ Transformation), where the three-phase stator currents are converted into a two-axis coordinate system (d-q frame) that rotates synchronously with the rotor's magnetic field. In the analysis, the zero component (I0) is not considered as the neutral of the three-phase induction motor is isolated and, hence, will not contain any information. This scalar value of the two frames generated is the Park Vector Modulus (PVM). The AC component of the PVM signal (PVAC) is extracted from PVM. PVM is shown as,

$$PVAC = PVM - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N PVM_n$$

The PVAC signals, hence generated, are shown,

Figure 5(a): Healthy Situation (at 100% load); Figure 5(b): Faulty Situation (Zone-2, at 100% load)

(a)

(b)

5. RESULTS

In this study, the generated PVAC signals are used for different time series transformation methods. Spectrogram (STFT) depicts a frequency-time representation, which helps in determining the abrupt changes in frequency due to the occurrence of a fault. Gramian Angular Field (GAF) converts the signals into angular matrices, which help in understanding time dependency. Markov Transition Field (MTF), as the name suggests, analyses state transitions in the PVAC signal and provides probable transitions caused by faults. A total of two loading conditions are shown here along with healthy situation.

Figure: 6(a), 7(a), 8(a): Healthy, Faulty (Zone-2, 75% load) and Faulty (Zone-2, 100% load) conditions using Spectrogram
Figure: 6(b), 7(b), 8(b): Healthy, Faulty (Zone-2, 75% load) and Faulty (Zone-2, 100% load) conditions using GAF
Figure: 6(c), 7(c), 8(c): Healthy, Faulty (Zone-2, 75% load) and Faulty (Zone-2, 100% load) conditions using MTF

The above images provide a qualitative comparison of the methods which allows to diagnose the fault. However, the images further validate the point that these faults are independent of the loading conditions.

To understand the similarity between these methods, three factors are taken into consideration,

- a) MSE (Mean Squared Error)
- b) PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio)
- c) SSIM (Structural Similarity Index)

For maximum similarity, MSE should be lower, and SSIM should be nearly equal to 1. However, PSNR is required higher to determine the best method out of these three. The table below helps in depicting a clear comparison.

Table 1: Similarity Analysis

Methods	MSE	PSNR	SSIM
STFT vs GAF	4484.26	11.63 dB	0.4212
STFT vs MTF	4144.99	11.99 dB	0.3714

From the analysis, it can fairly be concluded that Spectrogram and MFT have better signal-to-noise ratio, whereas Spectrogram and GAF have more structural similarity.

The data that is obtained in the form of images are meant to be used to diagnose faulty situations by training an AI model, i.e., CNN (Convolutional Neural Network). Hence, some other aspects are needed to be considered, such as,

- a) The method should be able to capture variations due to the occurrence of faults.
- b) The method should be able to distinguish between faulty and healthy conditions.
- c) Lastly, the method should be able to retain patterns that are linked to faulty situations.

The table below shows a qualitative comparison of the three mentioned methods on the basis of structural similarity, noise resistance, texture detail, and feature complexity.

Table 2: Comparison Table

Methods	Feature Complexity	Structural Similarity	Texture Detail	Noise Resistance
Spectrogram	Moderate	High	Low	High
GAF	High	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
MFT	Very High	Low	High	Low

From the comparison table above, we can now conclude that the GAF method has a higher ability to adapt complex fault patterns and has a pure balance between clarity and details by being not too smooth as well as not too noisy. Also, it has a moderate structural similarity, and hence, we can conclude that, Gramian Angular Field (GAF) is a highly appreciated method among all the methods to transform time series encoding images. This method is suitable enough to train CNN using the transformed images. However, it is advised to use Spectrogram as an auxiliary method for additional purposes.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The detection of misalignments in bearing in a three-phase squirrel cage induction motor is crucial for ensuring reliable and efficient operation in industrial applications. This project successfully implemented fault detection techniques to identify inner race defects using vibration analysis, motor current signature analysis (MCSA), and signal processing methods. The experimental results demonstrated that these techniques effectively diagnose faults at an early stage, minimizing the risk of catastrophic failures and unplanned downtime

By integrating advanced fault detection methods, this study contributes to predictive maintenance strategies, enhancing the motor's operational lifespan and efficiency. Future work could involve real-time

monitoring systems with artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms for more accurate and automated fault diagnosis. This project underscores the importance of early fault detection in industrial motors and provides a foundation for further research in condition-based monitoring techniques.

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